

Set-up of the 10 LL – ready for action

Milestones #35

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Abstract

This milestone report 35 documents the setting up of 10 LLs through a series of activities subsequent to the first Living Lab CoP meeting held on 19th and 20th April 2023, in Wageningen, Netherlands. The LL held interviews, and organised workshops in which they carried out a five-step roadmap exercise which included the definition of their LL boundaries as well as their problems, the identification of their stakeholders, the resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations they have access to, their gaps, and finally, the establishment of their action plan. The LL were required to submit reports of their workshop results, documenting their interactions, findings, and observations. This milestone report summarises these extensive LL reports, focusing on i) boundaries: aims and purposes, impacts and scope of activities; ii) Living Lab problem definition and barriers; iii) Stakeholders identification and analysis; iv) GAP analysis and resources and capabilities conditions assessment; and v) List of main actions from LL Action Plans.

It concludes with Reflections and Conclusions based on the reports and also the LL self-reflections on their progress from the initial CoP, through the interview and workshop process, to their final description of the outputs of the five-step process, their action plan, and lessons learned.

1. Introduction

1.1 The purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to give evidence for the Milestone 35 (Set-up of 10 Living Labs - ready for action). It describes what has been done resulting in action plans for each LL (ready for action!) and presents the initial observations with respect to Task 4.2 on the setting up of the CFD LLs. It can also be used as a document to monitor the progress made by the working group and the Living Labs so far.

1.2 Who is this document for

The usefulness of this document is mainly internal. The summarised results and methodology serve both for WP4 members to establish progress and further develop the necessary activities under a common thread and a coherent narrative, and for LL monitors and facilitators, who can use the main observations and learnings as inspiration for the implementation and continuation of their LLs. It could give foundation and inspiration for deliverables 4.2 and 4.3 to be produced in a later stage in the project. Additionally, interested parties outside these two groups may also benefit from this milestone serving as an informative document for the LLs within this project. The observations are based on the experience of each Living Lab.

1.3 The structure and logic of this document

In general terms, the "Introduction" aims to give a context to the outcomes presented in the subsequent section called "Summary of LL reports and selected observations", what has been done?, where do the results come from?, and who is involved? In the following section, selected outputs of the 10 LLs are summarised with the most relevant information extracted from each of the proposed steps, as well as the main learnings. Finally, a "Reflections and Conclusions" section refers to general observations and the reflections harvested from the LL on their progress made from the first CoP to the first 5 step LL Workshop. This is accompanied by a section of "Annexes". Due to the amount of material from which the document draws, and for reasons of length, they are not added in the main body of the text, but are available on links indicated herein.

1.4 Methodology

The objectives pursued within Task 4.2 (Analyses of situation & conditions and set up of the Living Labs), WP4 were the establishment of a clear working path for the setting up of 10 Living Labs and the analysis of the necessary and essential conditions for their success. For this reason, a methodology was established for the overall process, which provided guidance for the setting up of Living Labs within the Climate Farm Demo project. The guidelines (Annex 1) cover a comprehensive analysis of the situation and conditions, including the founding of Living Labs and the formulation of a strategy and action plan for the first year. In addition, they provide a roadmap for their forming, illustrated in Figure 1, helping them to identify conditions for their success. The description of the methodology of Task 4.2 is included in Deliverable D4.1 - Methodological framework for supporting and running the 10 Living Labs. These Living Labs have a structured framework for defining problems, delimiting boundaries, and addressing challenges, with a focus on innovation to co-create climate-smart solutions. The guidelines assist in the identification of resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCIs), as well as existing gaps in these areas, facilitating the identification of actions and the drafting of an initial action plan so as to transition to climate smart agriculture, and as well providing for a method to annually update strategies and action plans.

Figure 1. Summary of the 5 steps to analysis of situation & conditions and set up of the Living Labs.

Step 1 – Defining LL boundaries: Through this first step, the aim is to understand and delimit the LLs, according to their objectives, purposes, activities, and the context in which they are located. A Living Lab cannot do everything, and this step allows for defining initial parameters and possible impacts and results. It also serves as a basis for the subsequent steps.

Step 2 – LL problem definition: The primary goal of this second step is to outline the challenges faced by farmers and stakeholders in dealing with climate issues. It offers a framework to pinpoint the core climate problems addressed by LLs, shaping their purpose, and facilitating the integration of necessary innovations for accelerated solution development.

Step 3 – Stakeholder identification and analysis: This step is helpful in order to grasp the landscape of the LL situation, it is essential to comprehend the identity and involvement of stakeholders, recognizing their roles and influence in collaboratively shaping solutions. Thus, it is

vital to identify and maintain a balance among stakeholders emphasizing a multi-actor approach (MAA).

Step 4A – Identifying resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCIs) + GAP analysis:

This step aims to enhance the knowledge and skills of stakeholders by identifying and fostering future RCCIs. These are crucial for setting objectives based on available and missing RCCIs and they play a vital role in designing climate-smart solutions, solving problems, and scaling initiatives. Analysing RCCIs help to understand how actors respond to dynamic environments in the transition to sustainable agriculture. It also guides the formulation of an action plan by correlating objectives with identified problems and addressing the gap between current and desired states based on RCCIs.¹

Step 4B – Assessing conditions for co-creation, innovation, and transition:

This tool assesses LL conditions for co-creation, innovation, and transitioning to climate-smart farming, generating a spider diagram from a survey. LLs can easily evaluate their resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations, contributing to the strategy and action planning. It also allows for self-assessment and year-to-year comparisons throughout the project.

Step 5 – Strategy and action plan:

The action plan is crucial for defining concrete activities to achieve climate objectives, using existing RCCIs or addressing gaps in RCCIs as needed. Furthermore, it forms the basis for ongoing planning, provides data for monitoring and evaluation, and allows for periodic adjustments based on progress and lessons learned.

The process comprises these five iterative steps. It commenced with the establishment of the core group during the first meeting of the Community of Practitioners in Wageningen in 2023, then conducting stakeholder interviews (link to materials in ANNEX 2) and LL workshops to enhance stakeholder relationships and involvement (link to materials in ANNEX 3), to culminate in the enforcement of the Living Lab's strategy. During that process, 3 LLs' progress meeting have been done (link to materials in ANNEX 5). Subsequently, Living Lab teams iteratively fine-tune the collected results and data, actively contributing to the implementation of the action plan (link to reports from the LLs in ANNEX 4). The results obtained are also inputs for T4.3 and T4.4.

This Milestone report presents main highlights and initial outcomes of the process.

¹ More information could be found looking for the organisational theory based on resources and capabilities, encompassing the resource-based view of the firm (Barney 2001), dynamic capabilities (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997; Helfat and Peteraf, 2009), the knowledge-based view, (Kogut & Zander, 1992) and the relational view (Dyer & Singh, 1998).

1.5 What has been done and when

Table 1.Compilation of the 10 LLs workshops.

	LL name	Date of the annual LL Workshop	Location
#1	France - Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change	13/06/2023	INRAE FERLUS unit, Lusignan
#2	Germany – Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience	06/09/2023.	ATB Max-Eyth-Allee 100 14469 Potsdam
#3	Hungary - Water conserving soil cultivation practices	21/09/2023	Kujáni Tanya, Kecskemét, Talfája köz 139, 6000
#4	Italy - FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy	27/09/2023	Sala convegno Tecnopolo Piazzale Europa 1, Reggio Emilia
#5	Netherlands - Climate Smart Water Management LL	03/10/2023	WUR field crops Edelhertweg 1, 8219 PH Lelystad.
#6	Portugal - Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal	21/07/2023	Universidade de Évora, Pólo da Mitra Apartado 94, 7006-554 Évora
#7	Slovakia - Regenerative farming LL	18/10/2023	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Institute, Akademicka 4, 949 01 Nitra
#8	Spain - Almería Agroecology LL	27/10/2023	University of Almería, Ctra Sacramento S/N 04120, La Cañada de San Urbano, Edificio técnico V
#9	Sweden - Biogas Västra Skaraborg	20/10/2023	Kälströms Gård Essunga Källstorp 402, 465 93 Nossebro

#10	United Kingdom - Agroforestry in practice	10/11/2023	Whitehall Farm and Harvest Barn Farm Training Centre, Ramsey
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Table 2 below shows the different meetings that have been held with the LLs throughout 2023. The objectives of the meetings were to share questions and doubts about the process, the progress made to date, and the bottlenecks that each LL was encountering. To this end, each LL prepared in each session short presentations on its situation, challenges and included questions to other LLs (these materials can be found in Annex 5).

Table 2. Record of the LLs progress meetings. *Link to further materials in ANNEX 5

LL´s progress meetings		
Attendees	Date/Time	Link to minutes*
Group 1: UK, Hungary, Sweden, Spain, and Italy	26/06/23	Report meeting 26.06.2023.docx
Group 2: Slovakia, Portugal, France, Germany, and Netherlands	29/06/23	Report meeting 29.06.2023.docx
Group 1: Italy, France, Slovakia, Spain, UK, and Germany	11/09/23	Report meeting 11-09-23.docx
Group 2: Hungary, Sweden Netherlands, and Portugal	18/09/23	Report meeting 18-09-2023.docx
Group 1: Slovakia, Italy, Netherlands, France, and Spain	31/10/23	Report meeting 31.10.2023.docx
Group 2: Germany, Sweden, Hungary, Portugal, and UK	08/11/23	Report meeting 08.11.2023.docx

2. Summary of LL reports and selected observations

2.1 LL boundaries: aims and purposes, impacts and scope of activities

Table 3. Summary of the aims and purposes expected impacts and activities of the LLs.

<u>LL</u>	<u>Aims and purposes</u>	<u>Expected Impacts</u>	<u>Activities</u>
SLOVAKIA: Regenerative Farming LL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific validation of regenerative farming (RF) processes. - Promotion of RF practices for soil improvement. - Innovation strengthening through co-creation. - Knowledge expansion on RF in Slovakia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extension of proven regenerative farming methods and benefits. - Prevention of natural disasters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting practices of 10-year experience of RF in arable crops via demonstrations and dissemination activities.
ITALIA: FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To reduce emissions. - Enhancing soil health. - Efficient resource use. - Promotion of the information and adoption of the solution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher pig farm's profitability. - Reduce environmental impacts of the supply chain. - Influence other sectors (cheese or meat production/ dairy and beef cattle). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Application of the BiogasDoneRight® model. - Chemical/energy input reduction. - Biodiversity/crops rotations. - Animal feeding. - Socio-political and economic development.
HUNGARY: Water conserving soil cultivation practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop/adapt farming techniques to combat drought, soil degradation, climate change, and yield instability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased soil health in the region. - Improve local/regional economy. - Targets: Farmers not directly involved in LL and policy makers (adopting legislation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applied research and technology tests of soil conservation (RF). - Communication of results.
NETHERLANDS: Climate Smart Water Management LL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development and test of climate smart adaptive water solutions. - Facilitate dialogue and learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of solutions tailored to the local situation. - Promotion of a deeper understanding of water-issues and solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-creation of water solutions. - Support dialogue and learning around water issues.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support the establishment of a future proof climate resilient water system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test of a cost-benefit tool for water solutions. - Impacts on the resilience of the water management in the region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and test cost benefit tool. - Organisation of stakeholders' involvement.
<p>PORTUGAL: Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fight desertification in the region by promoting sustainable business models. - Fostering knowledge exchange. - Identifying private and public incentives. - Developing ecosystem services and creating social awareness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of local agriculture AKIS. - Farmer empowerment (with services and tools for technical advice). - Case study mapping and database. - Scaling ecosystem services. - Advisory capacity building. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experimentation. - Capacity building - Peer to peer (P2P) knowledge exchange.
<p>SPAIN: Almería Agroecology Living Lab</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a system of integrated control and management of water technologies. - Generation, storage, and reuse of water resource. - Knowledge transfer in value chain (increase learning and uptake) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable resource management (water footprint). - Social/Economic profitability and stability. - Technology for agricultural sector resilience, food production and industry inclusion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrations. - Stakeholder Network Building - Pilot testing. - Workshops and training. - Dissemination and communication.
<p>UK: Agroforestry in practice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contextualize silvoarable system as a climate smart farming practice. - Co-create digital training resources and a communication strategy. - Support farmer decision making. - Accelerate agroforestry adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge exchange through P2P learning sessions. - Co-Creation of practical solutions. - UK Agroforestry Farm Map/Pilot Farm Demonstrations. - Increased farmer confidence, decision making, and adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agroforestry literature review and UK needs identification. - Knowledge exchange events and co-creation. - Stakeholder engagement. - Roll out communication strategy (environmental and economic cost benefits)
<p>SWEDEN: Biogas Västra Skaraborg</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish farmer-owned biogas facility. - Improve manure efficiency, reduce GHG emissions, and increase soil organic matter. - Support farmers in setup, identify barriers/success factors, and provide recommendations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Better management of natural resources. - Reduction in GHG emissions. - Provide profit and a better fertilizer in return. - Better economy than many small farm plants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fund raising. - Permit acquisition. - Construction of the biogas plant and management plan. - Fair distribution of the subproducts.
<p>GERMANY: Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase livestock and mixed farm resilience. - Mitigate emissions. - Enhancing soil health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase technology adoption/awareness. - Identify main obstacles limiting adoption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tailor technology to the region. - Testing technologies. - Demonstrations and collection of data.

and increase farm resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-develop climate solutions. - Foster holistic thinking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-develop new/tailored solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient use of manures. - Improve animal welfare.
FRANCE: Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change, France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation of dairy cattle farms. - Build expertise and autonomy in livestock systems. - Improve experimentation. - Foster Holistic Thinking. 	<p><i>No information given, expected in future sessions.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Targets: Farmers, advisors, scientific research, animal/plant breeding organisations, citizens, environmental associations, administrative and public actors.... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing knowledge and experiences. - Explore and co-create solutions. - Set up action plans on volunteer farms. - Build an online community.

Observations on LL Boundaries and Aims:

Despite the diversity in the themes of the LLs, some of the expected impacts are repeated throughout all of the LLs. Such is the case of the dissemination of evidence and data:

“Extension of proven regenerative farming methods and benefits...”

“Promotion of a deeper understanding of water- issues and solutions...”

“Mapping current existent case studies and create a data base with relevant information...”

In addition, a common interest in the generation of data in the LLs' activities through experimentation, research, and co-development is noted:

“Applied research and technology tests of soil conservation techniques (regenerative agriculture) ...”

“Develop and test cost benefit tool and make results visible ...”

“Experimentation (on specific topics) and capacity building (directed to technical advisors and farmers) ...”

“Pilot testing...”

“Testing and co-development of technologies...”

These activities allow LLs to obtain empirical data to demonstrate to their stakeholders, promoting not only awareness, but also the adoption of climate-smart practices along the value chain. They all seek to impact greater resilience in the sectors they are involved in while searching for greater profitability and sustainability:

“Business economics (higher pig farm’s profitability) ...”

“Reduction of the environmental impact and improvement of farm’s profitability of other supply chain...”

“Improve local/regional economy...”

“To have an impact on the resilience of the water management and the capacity to address water challenges...”

“Social and economic stability...”

“Fair distribution of subproducts...”

“Improving the sustainability of food production (economic, environmental, and social) ...”

“Improving technologies to develop and build resilience in the local agricultural sector...”

“Environmental of the whole ham supply chain...”

“Increased soil health in the region...”

Furthermore, the need to inform and involve farmers from the outset is emphasised:

“Increased farmer confidence...”

“To equip farmers with services provided by knowledgeable stakeholders with the appropriate tools to give technical advice...”

“To support farmers in decision making and accelerate the adoption” ...

Promoting activities such as:

“Tailor the adoption of technologies to farms...”

“... and capacity building (directed to technical advisors and farmers) ...”

Finally, the need to exchange knowledge and foster learning among actors, through P2P learning, training, workshops, etc., is identified transversally both in the aims, expected impacts and activities. In addition, special relevance is given to all communication and dissemination activities:

“To transmit the information to the main stakeholders and to encourage the adoption of solution...”

“Communication of results: field day, workshops, etc...”

“To support learning and facilitate dialogue between stakeholders...”

“Organising learning events, exchange, and dialogue...”

“...fostering knowledge exchange...”

“Transferring these advances to the different actors and the value chain to increase learning, commitment, and uptake...”

“Workshops and training...”

“Dissemination, social networking, and communication...”

“Knowledge exchange through in-practice peer to peer learning sessions...”

“Knowledge exchange events and co-creation farmer sessions...”

“Roll out communication strategy...”

Related at the same time is the attention to the importance of involving stakeholders substantially and permanently over time (although not all mention this directly):

“Organising stakeholders’ involvement...”

“Stakeholder engagement in agroforestry activities...”

“Stakeholder network building...”

2.2 Living Lab problem definition and barriers

Table 4. Summary of LL problem definition and barriers.

<u>LL</u>	<u>Problem Definition</u>	<u>Barriers</u>
SLOVAKIA: Regenerative Farming LL	Declining soil quality jeopardizes farms, food access, sustainability, and property values. Insufficient evidence for RF benefits and weak soil policies exacerbates these risks.	No/minimum data to prove relevance. Lack of mutual trust (mainly among farmers).
ITALIA: FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy	Inadequate slurry management, excessive inputs, limited modernization and collaboration in farming and concerns about animal welfare, lead to a negative livestock reputation and reduced farm profitability.	Farmers and agronomical service providers show reluctance towards technological innovation. There's a persistent decline in farmers' remuneration (strong fluctuations in inputs and commodity prices).
HUNGARY: Water conserving soil cultivation practices	Develop or adapt farming techniques to combat drought, soil degradation, climate change, and yield fluctuations.	Consolidating new techniques with current legislation.
NETHERLANDS: Climate Smart Water Management LL	Higher pressure on water resources, leading to shortages. Climate-smart water solutions and water management are crucial responses.	Bringing stakeholders together and ensuring that these stakeholders carry the Living Lab.
PORTUGAL: Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal	The success of the Montado system depends on monitoring, technical knowledge, and value chain collaboration. Desertification in dryland areas requires urgent reversal efforts.	The main stakeholders are involved in different projects. It may be difficult to maintain the focus on the LL mission.
SPAIN: Almería Agroecology Living Lab	Scarcity and overexploitation of local water resources, with a notable absence of viable solutions for sustainable use. And the lack of awareness about the issue contributes to the conflict.	Cost of implementation related to scale. Resistance to change. Lack of knowledge of the current context. Dissemination and awareness of technologies. Lack/Failure of administrative resources to monitor compliance with the law. Lack of legislation to regulate. Infrastructure (typology of farms). Complexity of solutions

<p>UK: Agroforestry in practice</p>	<p>Agroforestry adoption is sluggish despite well-documented environmental benefits. Practical and economic considerations serve as persistent barriers to widespread implementation.</p>	<p>Simplify agroforestry research into practical workshops for new adopters.</p>
<p>SWEDEN: Biogas Västra Skaraborg</p>	<p>First of all, the government grant “Klimatklivet”, which accounts for 50 % of the capital to build the biogas plan, needs to be approved. After that, the management needs to make sure it is a fair organization among the owners and that the owners get value for their invested money.</p>	<p>Risk of not receiving national subsidies. Permits can take a long time so that capital starts to run out. Neighbours may appeal against local plan and environmental permit. Owners withdraw and sell their shares, resulting in less capital for investment.</p>
<p>GERMANY: Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience</p>	<p>Accepted business-as-usual practices, like inefficient manure use, persist due to a lack of practical alternatives. Despite this, there is a consensus on increased risks, decreased resilience, and higher costs.</p>	<p>Agricultural knowledge-transfer and connections to research are lacking in the region. Absence of public agricultural extension and farm advisors. Challenges in implementing available technologies/solutions due to practical, economic, administrative, and legal reasons.</p>
<p>FRANCE: Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change, France</p>	<p>Adapting to a drier climate requires coherent changes in forage production and dairy systems. However, implementing these changes at the scale of the production system or value chain poses challenges for farmers and the industry, particularly regarding limited irrigation water, leading to tensions in the region.</p>	<p>Lack of knowledge about alternatives among dairy farming actors. Need for reconfiguration of innovation systems... Lack of room for manoeuvre in financial aspects of farms.</p>

Observations on LLs barriers:

What is worth noting is that all LLs detected barriers and constraints that can be understood from a broad perspective as:

- Economic:

“Decline in farmers' remuneration (strong fluctuations in inputs and commodity prices) ...”

“Cost of implementation related to scale solutions...”

“Risk of not receiving national subsidies...”

“Lack of room for manoeuvre in financial aspects of farms...”

- Social:

“Lack of mutual trust (mainly among farmers) ...”

“Farmers and agronomical service providers show reluctance towards technological innovation...”

“Bringing stakeholders together and ensuring that these stakeholders carry the Living Lab...”

“The main stakeholders are involved in different projects. It may be difficult to maintain the focus on the LL mission...”

“Lack of knowledge of the current context. Dissemination and awareness of technologies...”

“Neighbours may appeal against local plan and environmental permit...”

“Lack of knowledge about alternatives among dairy farming actors...”

- Institutional:

“Consolidating new techniques with current legislation...”

“Lack/Failure of administrative resources to monitor compliance with the law. Lack of legislation to regulate...”

“Permits can take a long time so that capital starts to run out...”

“Absence of public agricultural extension and farm advisors...”

- Technical:

“No/minimum data to prove relevance...”

“Infrastructure (typology of farms). Complexity of solutions...”

“Challenges in implementing available technologies/solutions...”

“Need for reconfiguration of innovation systems...”

“Agricultural knowledge-transfer and connections to research are lacking in the region...”

“Simplify agroforestry research into practical workshops for new adopters...”

2.3 Stakeholders identification and analysis

Figure 2. Matrix for stakeholder analysis according to influence and interest.

In this stage, each LL had to classify the stakeholders previously identified in the four quadrants shown in Figure 2 (consult, involve, monitor, and inform), taking into account the influence and interest they could have in the development of the LL's activities.

Continuing with and despite the diversity of stakeholders recognised throughout the LLs, those that are repeatedly observed throughout the reports are presented. Emphasis is placed on the most significant quadrants, "involve", i.e. the stakeholders with the highest influence and interest, and the "monitor" quadrant, i.e. the actors with the least influence and interest. The chosen stakeholders are positioned in these quadrants in a generic way, although there are discrepancies within the context of each LL.

Please note that these results are the outcome of an initial stakeholder analysis. Stakeholders identified as more or less relevant are subject to change, and in further analysis, their interest and influence may evolve. For example, a bank with "green" loans or carbon credits could be very important in a given situation. This will allow us to compare over the years how the stakeholder quadrants have transformed.

Recurring stakeholders throughout LLs with a relevant interest and influence, i.e. positioned in the "involved" quadrant:

- **Farmers and farmer/producer associations:** Seen as key elements. They are positioned in the center of the diagram as an indicator of their relevance or in the "involve" quadrant, which shows that they have a significant influence regardless of the context of the LL.
- **Advisors:** Positioned very close to farmers in general, they are seen as key elements in the adoption of improved practices. In some LLs they are positioned in the "consult" quadrant, but still with a great deal of influence.
- **Research centers:** Perceived as having high interest and medium-high influence. They enable the development of data-driven tools and methodologies. They are taken into account in most LLs.
- **Public administration:** Essential actors due to their influence, oversee and regulate policies, with the aim of fostering development and equity.
- **Certifiers:** Identified in those LLs that seek to add value to the climate-smart practices that are carried out.
- **Industry:** Positioned in 3 of the 4 quadrants due to their influence, the auxiliary industry provides essential inputs and services, optimising productivity to boost efficiency and sustainability.

- **Disseminators:** In relation to the importance of reaching the widest possible audience, these types of actors are included in some of the LLs.
- **Experimental farms:** This is a fundamental element in demonstrating the benefits of the practices and methods that are carried out.

Repetead stakeholders with less influence and interest along the LLs, i.e. in the "monitor" quadrant:

- **Consumers:** placed in the bottom quadrants, with influence but medium interest.
- **Funding sources/Banks:** They are also recognized for having a significant influence in the case of affecting the financial resources available in the context of the LL. Although they are mentioned more as elements to monitor.
- **Local governemnt:** It can affect the resources available at the local level of each LL, which is why they are located in the monitoring quadrant primarily.

2.4 GAP analysis and resources and capabilities conditions assessment

Table 5. Presentation of the gaps in resources and capabilities identified by the LLs.

LL	Focus area	Gaps
SLOVAKIA: Regenerative Farming LL	<i>No information given, expected in future sessions.</i>	<i>No information given, expected in future sessions.</i>
ITALIA: FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy	Reduction GHG and NH3 emissions and increasing the soil organic matter applying the principles of the "BiogasDoneRight®" model in the heavy pig production chain.	It is necessary to develop supply chain contracts to give added value to the product and seek additional forms of private financing... Create of a national platform for information sharing... ...Development of new regional DSS systems; of the tools for evaluation, of new solutions...
HUNGARY: Water conserving soil cultivation practices	Enhanced soil moisture retention (drought)/ Intercropping.	Ability of local farmer communities to share the identified good practices/technologies. Reach out and engage more local stakeholders... Long term involvement and engagement of stakeholders...
NETHERLANDS: Climate Smart Water Management LL	The establishment of a future proof climate resilient water system in the Veenkoloniën (peat colonies).	Financial support for stakeholder facilitation... LL needs additional support from other stakeholders to further expand the LL... Farmers organisation that thinks along in the LL formation. Local people that can recognise suitable solutions for the LL region.
PORTUGAL: Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal	Soil analysis, forest renovation, carbon sequestration, ecosystem services and advisory training/ capacity building.	Linking projects' information to avoid farmer fatigue on data collection. Delivering results in: Technical agronomical training, Co-creation training Framework for adaptation and mitigation plans. / Framework based on the soil health benchmark.

<p>SPAIN: Almería Agroecology Living Lab</p>	<p>Transfer these advances to actors and the value chain.</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about the problem is itself part of the conflict.</p>	<p>We find a gap in the available financial, human, and organisational resources...</p> <p>There is a significant gap in LL's capability to disseminate knowledge and demonstrate cost-effectiveness...</p> <p>Strategy to continue the engagement of contacts...</p>
<p>UK: Agroforestry in practice</p>	<p>Development of a platform to facilitate information exchange, establishment, management market access and links to relevant research. To provide a mechanism for P2P learning and farmer training.</p> <p>Practical elements and direct access to simple economic models are a missing link.</p>	<p>Road map of Living Lab events and costs.</p>
<p>SWEDEN: Biogas Västra Skaraborg</p>	<p>Establish a cooperatively owned biogas plant that utilizes manure in a resource efficient manner while reducing greenhouse gases.</p>	<p>Lack of half of the funding (loans, share capital...)</p> <p>Government support for biogas production.</p> <p>A network of contacts with knowledge of the suppliers</p> <p>Technical insight and knowledge of the substrate mix</p> <p>Establish contact with energy buyers, industry, gas buyers. / New contacts to bring in more/different kind of substrates, plant growers...</p>
<p>GERMANY: Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience</p>	<p>Improved manure management / adaptation and mitigation of impacts in cropping systems and animal housings of livestock and mixed farms.</p>	<p>Data transfer and management; stakeholder engagement...</p> <p>Capability to involve stakeholders...</p> <p>Other technology providers, local policy makers, schools/public informed.</p> <p>Organisational and economic innovations.</p>
<p>FRANCE: Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change, France</p>	<p>Explore and experiment collectively the strategies, organisations, and practices by which dairy farming systems could adapt to CC and mitigate it in Poitou Charentes</p>	<p>Time and financial resources to develop the means of communication more proactively.</p> <p>Connect more specifically and easily with value chains aspects...</p> <p>More public actors and representatives of non-agricultural actors.</p>

Observations on the overlapping gaps with respect to resources and capabilities:

Considering the different needs of the LLs, a pattern could be detected in the resources and capabilities that the LLs describe throughout their reports.

For the most part, there is a gap in the human resources available or existing in the LLs as well as a lack in collaborations:

“New contacts to bring in more/different kind of substrates, influence plant growers to adapt their cultivation...”

“More public actors and representatives of non-agricultural actors...”

“Other technology providers, local policy makers, schools/public informed...”

“Establish contact with energy buyers, industry, gas buyers...”

“Local people that can recognise suitable solutions for the LL region...”

Consequently, and as seen in previous sections, there is an important interest in the dissemination and communication of results, activities, benefits, costs, etc. This is reflected in the weaknesses identified by the LLs:

“There is a significant gap in LL's capability to disseminate knowledge and demonstrate cost-effectiveness...”

“Create of a national platform for information sharing; improvement of training courses for the actors who are involved in the LL...”

“Ability of local farmer communities to share the identified good practices/technologies. ...”

“Delivering results in: Technical agronomical training, Co-creation training...”

Emphasis is also placed on the lack of capabilities on the part of LLs to strengthen and engage stakeholders, these gaps are aligned with some of the barriers identified:

“Strategy to continue the engagement of contacts we already have, and to further involve farmers and key actors such as irrigation communities and public institutions...”

“Capability to involve stakeholders...”

“Reach out and engage more local stakeholders throughout the innovation development process...”

“Long term involvement and engagement of a wide range of motivated and willing stakeholders impacted by the potential innovation...”

“LL needs additional support from other stakeholders to further expand the LL and develop a climate smart water solution...”

“Farmers/farmer organisation that thinks along in the LL formation...”

Something common also found through LLs is the lack of economic resources:

“Time and financial resources to develop the means of communication more proactively...”

“...economic innovations...”

“Lack of half of the funding (loans, share capital...) ...”

“We find a gap in the available financial...”

“...seek additional forms of private financing...”

The identified gap reflects the lack of resources and technical capabilities:

“Data transfer and management...”

“Technical insight...”

“...development of new regional DSS systems; Development of the tools for the evaluation of the economic-environmental sustainability; Development of new solutions...”

Gaps are detected at the level of resources and organizational capabilities:

“Organisational [...] innovations.”

“Road map of Living Lab events and costs.”

“Framework for adaptation and mitigation plans.”

“Framework based on the soil health benchmark.”

Finally, some LLs occasionally detect gaps in their available institutional resources:

“Government support for [...] production.”

And in the ability to add value to the practices they carry out:

“Connect more specifically and easily with value chains aspects (economics, logistics, legal issues, etc.), relying on concerned actors.”

“It is necessary to develop supply chain contracts to give added value to the product”.

These gaps found in the different resources and capabilities of the LLs are reflected in the spider diagrams that each LL recorded, and which can be seen in Table 7 of this document, section 4.

2.5 List of main actions from LL Action Plans

Table 6. Compilation of the set-up actions of LLs.

<u>LL</u>	<u>List of actions</u>
SLOVAKIA: Regenerative Farming LL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop relevant methodologies. • Apply methodologies /Sampling at farm. • Processing data & creating digital map.
ITALIA: FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the number of stakeholders to involve in the LL. • To monitor technical instruments for environmental evaluation and technical economic support mechanism. • To organize physical and on-line demo farm's events. • To improve farmers training. • To favour the dissemination of the obtained results.
HUNGARY: Water conserving soil cultivation practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up experiments with autumn-sown cultures. • Initial state soil sampling. • Organising laboratory analysis. • Evaluation and analysis of the research data. • LL multistakeholder workshop (2nd).
NETHERLANDS: Climate Smart Water Management LL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and test concrete solutions in practice, such as excavating sand heads and above ground water storage to address water scarcity. Later other solutions may be tested e.g. with farmers around the FotF. • Information sessions and workshops for local arable farmers and other stakeholders to raise awareness and exchange experiences on the challenges of climate change and drought in the Veenkoloniën. • Developing a tool that gives farmers insight into the costs and benefits of implementing climate smart water solutions on farm level.
PORTUGAL: Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Data base. • Collect a soil health analysis benchmark from the ongoing projects. • Forest renovation. • Analyse Carbon sequestration in the montado. • Analyse soil-based Ecosystem services. • Review and analyse pass training program dedicated to technical advisors.
SPAIN: Almería Agroecology Living Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consideration of the creation of an operating group and seeking of funds • Techno-economic technology assessment (benchmarking) • Open days (demonstrations, trainings) • Pilot testing
UK: Agroforestry in practice	No information given, expected in future sessions.

<p>SWEDEN: Biogas Västra Skaraborg</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide in substrate mix (need to bring in more substrates). • Selection of supplier for the biogas plant and technology. • Market and sale of gas and other products produced at the biogas plant.
<p>GERMANY: Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the number of stakeholders and the engagement level. • Co-design mitigation and adaptation practices at field and barn level • Disseminate results, organize demo events, organize periodical LL meetings
<p>FRANCE: Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change, France</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise 2 yearly meetings and build the community of concern. • Co-design and experiment CC adaptation practices within the network. • Coordinate and anchor the LL events with other actors' networks and innovation dynamics.

Observations on the list of actions:

To a greater or lesser extent within the diversity of actions that each LL has distinguished as appropriate according to its context and related to its aims, problems, barriers, and available resources and capabilities in general terms in this first phase of establishing a LL, all plan to generate and analyse data through experiments and testing, seeking relations with research centres or institutes.

In addition, throughout all the steps evaluated, it has been seen that one of the main concerns and objectives in most LLs is the dissemination of results, therefore, activities such as workshops, trainings, open days, demonstrations, peer-to-peer learning sessions, etc., are seen in the list of actions.

To conclude, it should not be forgotten that further to the environmental perspective pursued by LLs, producers, and actors involved in the sector seek economic profitability. Thus, we see approaches to collecting and expanding data in terms of costs and benefits, even in some cases making a more general comparison in the market (benchmarking).

Reviewing the reports of the LLs, some reflections are extracted about how the proposed methodology of the 5 steps has helped in the development and refinement of the different action plans and the set-up of the LLs:

“After having contact with local stakeholders, we were able to better define concrete actions for the upcoming months. During the CoP in Wageningen, these actions were still quite vague. Now, we have defined our next steps.”

“The exact type and number of soil cultivation experiments as well as the farmers participating in the experimentation have been specified and collated during the LL workshop. This in turn, enabled the LL to come up with a more comprehensive set of actions, timings, identification of the stakeholders involved, as well as resources needed to carry out the initial set of experiments.”

“The discussion between the workshop participants allowed us to better identify other stakeholders who can be involved in the LL to encourage the diffusion of the proposed Climate Smart Agriculture strategy. In the workshop it emerged that the diffusion of Climate Smart Agriculture practices could be favoured by the appropriate training of farmers, technicians and sector operators; consequently, it is necessary to organize training courses because these are often not carried out by specialized personnel.”

“The action plan outlined in the first CoP meeting was substantially modified, evolving into more precise actions targeted to clearer aims and to co-develop more concrete CS solutions.”

“The action plan has developed from a general conceptual framework on how to assemble the network to a more concrete set of research related actions.”

3. Reflections and Conclusions

As part of the process of reporting on the 5 steps of the roadmap outlined above in Introduction section and expanded on above, LLs were asked to reflect on how their understanding of their LL had developed since the CoP meeting in Wageningen where they were first introduced to the concepts and roadmap of setting up their LL, which included holding interviews and organizing workshops. We summarise below the highlights, and more detail can be found in Table 7 below, in particular the assessment “spider diagrams” carried out by 8 of the 10 LLs.

With respect to the definition of the **LL boundaries**, we see that most LL developed a more focused approach, although some also became aware of other related transversal issues or activities, such as training, economic analysis, experimental testing or exploring value chain lock-ins. In one case, during exploratory interviews with other stakeholders it became evident that the activities of the LL overlapped with other very similar initiatives, so the boundaries were reworked to include collaboration amongst such entities and the clarification of roles. It was also noted that a better focus and alignment between the aim of the LL and the problems chosen, would more likely lead to more promising interaction with stakeholders.

After the first internal meeting and following the initial feedback from WP4, it was possible to restrict the aim of the LL to topics more closely related to the activities [...] with better chances to allow a promising interaction with stakeholders.

In another LL, after the CoP and subsequent Workshop, the LL decided to focus on knowledge exchange and farmer training, rather than focusing on specific solutions for identified climate problem.

Following the [...] workshops and the LL CoP meeting [...] we have adapted the ... LL ... to focus on the development of a platform to facilitate information exchange between farmers & stakeholders across planning, establishment, management market access and links to relevant research etc and to provide a mechanism for peer-to-peer learning and farmer training. This better aligns with the needs of those seeking to adopt agroforestry in the UK, from what is a relatively low baseline agroforestry area.

While not as radical, stakeholders of another LL expressed the need to consider aspects such as markets, heterogeneity of farm activities and structure and the feasibility and probability of LL solutions to be explored in considering its boundaries.

The refining of the **Problem Definition** was seen in varying degrees across the LLs, and in most cases, LL reduced the scope of problems to be addressed or refined its focus. For several LL it became apparent that knowledge and its dissemination was at the core of the climate problem-solution presented. This led to thinking about new ways to spread existing knowledge, through platforms, new collaborations, or training programs. The link between boundaries and the definition of problems to be dealt with was well noted.

The LL workshop helped to refine the aim of the LL and to narrow the selection of problems to be addressed and solutions to be co-developed.

With respect to the **identification and analysis of stakeholders**, during the time frame between the CoP and the Workshop, LL both expanded and reduced the number of stakeholders involved in the LL, some discovering stakeholders with impact, recognising gaps in knowledge and expertise that stakeholders could bring, while other LL considering that a core group of committed shareholders was most appropriate to help clearly define and set up the LL. Different levels or “rings” of stakeholders were noticed, from farm or production level to community level, which made a homogeneous approach to LL stakeholders difficult. As well, LL noted that it was possible that there would be a rotating group of stakeholders as the LL progressed and adapted, thus suggesting that a dynamic approach to stakeholder identification and engagement was necessary where active inclusion of new actors needed to be anticipated. As well, the diverse knowledge of people within the same institutional shareholder was discovered.

Within the board and the stakeholder organisation, there is more knowledge about the different parts of the project than we first knew [...] we realised that it was important to interview everyone on the board [...], since it was composed of people with different knowledge and backgrounds.

While **resources and capabilities** proved a challenging concept for some in the CoP, walking through the 5 steps in the Workshop seemed to allow a better understanding of these, the overall resulting gaps, and the crafting of an action plan.

We have a better view of the capabilities and resources (e.g., available technological resources and stakeholders). Owing to a better understanding of the aim of the LL, we have also a better understanding of the existing gaps (for instance, human resources). The view on these was very blurred after the first CoP meeting.

...

The initial idea was to focus the LL mainly in generating ecosystem services associated with the montado. This is still one of the final aims of the LL but after working on the RCCI analysis with the key stakeholders we have been able to prioritize the research tasks that we must follow through with the final aim. Additionally, we have identified the trust/knowledge gap that exists in advisory services in farmers associations that work directly in the montado mixed system.

...

The identification of the RCCIs has matured throughout the phases and it has become more and more precise and focused on what we want to do in this LL. Thanks to the interviews and the workshop [...]. The gap analysis has been clarified, at the beginning it was not clear what LL’s needs were and therefore what were the requirements that needed to be covered. During the workshop, [resources and capabilities] were revealed spontaneously and precisely, allowing again to clarify the “hot spots” that need to be addressed.

From another angle, understanding more clearly the technical/scientific focus of the LL helped to understand resources and capabilities:

Identification of RCCI and the GAP has been clarified since the CoP. This was enabled by the LL kick-off workshop help locally, where we were successful in identifying the types and nature of experiments to be carried out by the LL in the coming year, therefore the resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations needed by the LL could also be more directly identified.

The **assessment** or “spider diagram” further assisted the LL to understand an integrated approach to the resources, capabilities, and gaps. Many LLs were able to understand the relationship quite concisely between various resources and capabilities:

The [spider] diagram shows the collaborations will play an essential part in the establishment and conduct of the LL. Indeed, the most relevant obstacle will be the information exchange and operational articulation between the key stakeholders.

...

Analysing the spider diagram, we can say that the financial and human resources must be improved, with specific emphasis on the latter regard. Collaborations could partially cope with the lack of human resources, but they should also be improved. This partially hampers the capability to cope with technical and management issues and with the capacity to scale up CS solutions.

Certain LLs were able to use the classification of resources and capabilities provided to add more precision to their analysis:

The spider web gives us insight in what to work on and where to create focus for the action plan. (Translated from Dutch:) In particular, we need to get more support from the network (including farmers) for the LL. In the web these are Human resources and Collaboration resources. In addition, we still have to work on trust (we are suddenly working on something new) and on upscaling (that is not yet our focus). These are capabilities “to scale” and “collaboration capability” in the spider web).

For the most part, **Action Plans** experienced significant changes and refinements, developing beyond the CoP meeting.

The action plan outlined in the first CoP meeting was substantially modified, evolving into more precise actions targeted to clearer aims and to co-develop more concrete CS solutions.

...

The exact type and number of soil cultivation experiments as well as the farmers participating in the experimentation have been specified and collated during the LL workshop [...]. This in turn, enabled the LL to come up with a more comprehensive set of actions, timings, identification of the stakeholders involved, as well as resources needed to carry out the initial set of experiments. This action plan is a more accurate illustration of the timing as well as stakeholders involved in the testing of technologies, than previously outlined at the Wageningen CoP workshop.

LL also became aware of the potential of their revised action plans to join forces and leverage resources to create more impact:

While discussing with these partners our initial view of the LL, we came to understand the enormous potential to integrate the ongoing work developed in different projects about specific relatable topics [...]. Thus, the LL becomes a cradle for integrated innovation practices. The partners’ complementarity between research, advisory, and experimentation give us the opportunity to integrate our work and produce results (tools, practices, training material, etc.) with strong sustainability strategies enabling innovation uptake along the chain.

Across several LLs, actions related to training of farmers, technicians and advisory services were mentioned.

In the workshop it emerged that the diffusion of Climate Smart Agriculture practices could be favoured by the appropriate training of farmers, technicians, and sector operators;

consequently, it is necessary to organize training courses because these are often not carried out by specialized personnel.

Various LL also mentioned the necessity to understand the economics and market forces involved. One LL succinctly pointed out that the action plan should also consider the need for adequate indicators, models and tools.

To properly evaluate the effectiveness of the application of Climate Smart Agriculture strategies proposed by our LL it is also necessary to have adequate indicators, models and tools.

The Table 7 below is a more extensive summary of Reflections by the LL, but overall, we can see that the 5-step process taken in the workshops contributed to significant advancement of the setting up of the LL across the CFD project.

Table 7. Reflections on development of the LL after carrying out LL Workshop 5 steps.

<u>LL country</u>	<u>Reflections:</u>
SLOVAKIA: Regenerative Farming LL	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The boundaries were developed in a more concrete manner:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Around a challenge – healthy and environmentally sustainable soil (healthy soil – healthy food-healthy people) -Geographically/regionally – considering Western Slovakia, in longer term perspective the entire territory of Slovakia -By sector – Arable crops – major impact on soil quality (area based) -By users – farmers, gardeners -By stakeholders – open, landowners <p>-Through a coordination entity- Leading farm in regenerative farming in SK (lighthouse farm) with a support of BEC (coordination of LL - RF farms)</p> <p>Problem Definition: The main definition has not changed drastically but few minor changes were identified.</p> <p>ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: <i>Several changes were made to core stakeholders:</i> SUA (Slovak University of Agriculture) – out for now (compare to Wageningen); IZPI (The Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Institute) – in; SPPK (Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber) – lower interest as expected.</p> <p>Action Plan: Since RF (regenerative farming) is relatively new approach, there are minimum valuable RF-related documents, guidelines, materials (videos) to learn from – <i>it is crucial to collect maximum sources providing expertise in RF to be widely used - this is important mainly for scalability of LL RF.</i></p>

	<p><i>In this respect it is crucial to strengthen capacities of advisors through various training modules (to be developed, prepared, tested, ...</i></p>																														
<p>ITALIA: FERTY - Feed fertilization crops and energy</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The main LL structure has been maintained, as well the aims. <i>From the semistructured interviews and the workshop, further aspects emerged that will be taken into account, such as the need to evaluate the economic sustainability and training for farmers and agricultural service providers.</i> The <i>clarification of the roles</i> of feed mills, public institutions and certification bodies has also emerged.</p> <p>Problem Definition: <i>From the discussion, additional problems were realized, such as the poor and sometimes not right training for the farmers and agronomic service providers</i> and the necessity to involve animal feed factory for incentives diets with less protein content; <i>consequently, among the actions that could be developed in the LL we can consider organizing training courses and trying to involve producers of animal feed.</i></p> <p>ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: The <i>stakeholder’s panorama was expanded to training bodies, agricultural service providers and feeding milling.</i></p> <p>Resources & Capabilities: The discussion that took place between all the stakeholders who participated in the workshop and the result of the GAP analysis did not lead us to modify the idea of LL development that we presented to the Wageningen Cop, but <i>it helped us to understand what other potential stakeholders to involve and which activities will need to be most developed over time.</i></p> <p>Assessment: Analysing the results obtained from the spider diagram we can say that the <i>material and financial resources, collaborations and technological innovations proposed in the LL must be improved and to do this, greater sharing of ideas and greater cooperation between stakeholders is necessary</i>, even if those present at the workshop, they showed a high aptitude for communication and the exchange of ideas. <i>Greater technological development is also necessary</i>, and this can be favoured by the greater presence of public or private funding sources.</p> <div data-bbox="475 1415 1375 2004" data-label="Figure"> <p>Assessment of the LL conditions (combined)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>R&C assessment (Score)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Material r.</td><td>5</td></tr> <tr><td>Financial r.</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>Human r.</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Organisational r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Technological r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaborations r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovations r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>TM issues</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Attitudes & values</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Absoptive cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Adaptive cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovation cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaboration cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Cap. To scale</td><td>2</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div>	Category	R&C assessment (Score)	Material r.	5	Financial r.	4	Human r.	3	Organisational r.	2	Technological r.	2	Collaborations r.	2	Innovations r.	2	TM issues	2	Attitudes & values	2	Absoptive cap.	2	Adaptive cap.	2	Innovation cap.	2	Collaboration cap.	2	Cap. To scale	2
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	<p>Action Plan: The discussion between the workshop participants allowed us to better identify other stakeholders who can be involved in the LL to encourage the diffusion of the proposed Climate Smart Agriculture strategy. In the workshop it emerged that the diffusion of Climate Smart Agriculture practices could be favoured by the appropriate training of farmers, technicians, and sector operators; consequently, it is necessary to organize training courses because these are often not carried out by specialized personnel.</p> <p>To properly evaluate the effectiveness of the application of Climate Smart Agriculture strategies proposed by our LL it is also necessary to have adequate indicators, models, and tools.</p>
<p>HUNGARY: Water conserving soil cultivation practices</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The definition of boundaries has not changed since the CoP. We had quite a clear picture and definition of the boundaries due to previous on farm activities in the area. It's worth mentioning that it has become apparent, that smaller steps have to be taken in light of current cultivation practices than expected. In terms of involving a wide range of stakeholders in the initial LL workshop, there were difficulties arising with conflicting time schedules of various stakeholders i.e. Authorities (this was not due to disinterest, but rather a timing issue), or higher education representatives from the local university who had to leave during the workshop due to other commitments.</p> <p>Problem Definition: Collectively agreed on new techniques and practices that will potentially bring us closer to the solution of the outlined problem.</p> <p>ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: The initial idea and identification of potential stakeholders have been mostly accurate. Some clarifications have been made in terms of their roles and level of involvement in the LL.</p> <p>Resources & Capabilities: Identification of RCCI and the GAP has been clarified since the CoP. This was enabled by the LL kick-off workshop help locally, where we were successful in identifying the types and nature of experiments to be carried out by the LL in the coming year, therefore the resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations needed by the LL could also be more directly identified. At this point the LL is at the initial stage in terms of actual experimentation etc, therefore it is worth mentioning, that questions relating to what adaptive capabilities etc. the LL will need is not applicable at this point in time.</p> <p>Assessment: In terms of financial resources, the national research grant is awarded for the next 2 years. This will contribute to the LL and will inform and enable the LL</p>

	<p>innovation development (experimentation) process in the relatively short term (2 years) at this point.</p> <div data-bbox="459 342 1369 969" data-label="Figure"> <p>Assessment of the LL conditions (combined)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>R&C assessment (Score)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Material r.</td><td>5</td></tr> <tr><td>Financial r.</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>Human r.</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Organisational r.</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Technological r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaborations r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovations r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>TM issues</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Attitudes & values</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Absoptive cap.</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Adaptive cap.</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovation cap.</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Cap. To scale</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaboration cap.</td><td>1</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <p>Action Plan: The <i>exact type and number of soil cultivation experiments as well as the farmers participating in the experimentation have been specified and collated during the LL workshop, in Hungary. This in turn, enabled the LL to come up with a more comprehensive set of actions, timings, identification of the stakeholders involved, as well as resources needed to carry out the initial set of experiments. This action plan is a more accurate illustration of the timing as well as stakeholders involved in the testing of technologies, than previously outlined at the Wageningen CoP workshop.</i></p>	Category	R&C assessment (Score)	Material r.	5	Financial r.	4	Human r.	3	Organisational r.	3	Technological r.	2	Collaborations r.	2	Innovations r.	2	TM issues	1	Attitudes & values	1	Absoptive cap.	1	Adaptive cap.	1	Innovation cap.	1	Cap. To scale	1	Collaboration cap.	1
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<p>NETHERLANDS: Climate Smart Water Management LL</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: During the Wageningen CoP we identified the rough boundaries. Together with the main stakeholders we have specified the boundaries of the LL. The interviews helped to create better understanding of the challenges and possibilities in the Veen kolonien region and what is already done by other stakeholders and initiatives, what is needed and what helped to specify the focus of the LL. In this way the LL has better defined its specific role and niche. After Wageningen CoP we have narrowed it down to the specific solution of above ground water storage, but then widened the focus again to encompass all different climate smart water solutions and a strategy to zoom in and out, to combine a focus on a specific solution with a wider focus this allows us to evolve with developments in the LL participants, the contexts, and the other projects.</p> <p>Problem Definition: During the CoP meeting in Wageningen we formulated a very broad topic on ‘the water problem’ in the Netherlands. However, after the interviews and workshop we were able to set boundaries for our problem and have better tailored the problem statement to and with the LL area.</p> <p>ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: Initially, we had thought of having as many stakeholders as possible participate directly in the formation of the Living Lab. Eventually it turned out to be more suitable to determine the scope of the LL with</p>																														

	<p>a core group, based on conversations and interviews with other stakeholders. The LL will further evolve, and the involvement of relevant other further stakeholders is a point of constant attention.</p> <p>Resources & Capabilities: During the CoP in Wageningen, it was hard to already look into specific gaps within the needs of the LL. However, after speaking with stakeholder parties and being in close contact with Farm of the Future, we gained more insight in overall gaps necessary for further LL development.</p> <p>Assessment: The spider web gives us insight in what to work on and where to create focus for the action plan. (translated from Dutch: In particular, we need to get more support from the network (including farmers) for the LL. In the web these are Human r. and Collaboration r. In addition, we still have to work on trust (we are suddenly working on something new) and on upscaling (that is not yet our focus). These are capabilities to scale and collaboration capability in the spider web).</p> <div data-bbox="454 786 1401 1357" data-label="Figure"> <table border="1"> <caption>Assessment of the LL conditions (combined) - R&C assessment</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>R&C assessment (approx. value)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Material r.</td><td>4.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Financial r.</td><td>4.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Human r.</td><td>2.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Organisational r.</td><td>3.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Technological r.</td><td>3.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaborations r.</td><td>2.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovations r.</td><td>2.0</td></tr> <tr><td>TM issues</td><td>1.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Attitudes & values</td><td>1.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Absorptive cap.</td><td>2.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Adaptive cap.</td><td>2.5</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovation cap.</td><td>3.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Cap. To scale</td><td>3.5</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <p>Action Plan: After having contact with local stakeholders, we were able to better define concrete actions for the upcoming months. During the CoP in Wageningen, these actions were still quite vague. Now, we have defined our next steps.</p>	Category	R&C assessment (approx. value)	Material r.	4.5	Financial r.	4.0	Human r.	2.5	Organisational r.	3.5	Technological r.	3.0	Collaborations r.	2.5	Innovations r.	2.0	TM issues	1.5	Attitudes & values	1.5	Absorptive cap.	2.0	Adaptive cap.	2.5	Innovation cap.	3.0	Cap. To scale	3.5
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<p>PORTUGAL: Montado. Fighting desertification in the South of Portugal</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: Initially we envisioned a LL focused on generating Ecosystem Services for the montado region. Through several meetings held with EDIA, we have come to know that another LL on the montado system was being idealized by Universidade de Évora. As such, it was agreed that the best route would be to join efforts and let Universidade de Évora coordinate the LL with support from Consulai. During the workshop with all the stakeholders identified (at that moment) it became clear that several partners were involved in different projects with focus on the montado system. The thematic areas of these projects were grouped in: Soil Health Practices, Development of Ecosystem Services, Grazing, Montado Regeneration, and Technical Training/Capacity Building. The ongoing projects in which the stakeholders were involved helped drawing the picture of a common effort towards fighting desertification in the montado region.</p>																												

Problem Definition: The problem has not changed, but it has since been described in more detail (and more information was collected).

ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: With the assistance of the core stakeholders, we have **enlarged the stakeholder analysis** in several aspects. In terms of experimental stations, local policy makers, R&D enterprises, and public certifying agencies.

Resources & Capabilities: The initial idea was to focus the LL manly in generating ecosystem services associated with the montado. This is still one of the final aims of the **LL but after working on the RCCI analysis with the key stakeholders we have been able to prioritize the research tasks that we must follow-through with the final aim. Additionally we have identified the trust/knowledge gap that exists in advisory services in farmers associations that work directly in the montado mix-system**

Assessment: The **diagram shows the collaborations will play and essential part in the establishment and conduct of the LL.** Indeed, the **most relevant obstacle will be the information exchange and operational articulation between the key stakeholders** that, in turn, are involved in several projects. We must guarantee the LL does not become an initiative running on the background of these organization but rather stimulates activities and innovation uptake in the rest of the network. It is also noticeable the smaller relevance given to resources, since we plan to build this on the ongoing projects efforts in the montado region. Despite not being directly related in the key stakeholders, the **outreach of the LL will depend on the capacity of transferring these capabilities. Also, worth mentioning the absorptive capabilities will be a key factor referring to the training and knowledge exchange programs we aim to produce.**

Action Plan: The action plan has developed from a general conceptual framework on how to assemble the network to a more concrete set of research related actions. This derives from the cooperation between the three key stakeholders (Consulai, Uni.Évora, and EDIA). While discussing with these partners our initial view of the LL, **we came to understand the enormous potential to integrate the ongoing work developed in different projects about specific relatable topics in the montado. Thus, the LL**

	<p><i>becomes a cradle for integrated innovation practices. The partners complementarity between research, advisory, and experimentation give us the opportunity to integrate our work and produce results (tools, practices, training material, etc.) with strong sustainability strategies enabling innovation uptake along the chain.</i></p>
<p>SPAIN: Almería Agroecology Living Lab</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The main points we have picked up since the boundary's definition in Wageningen have been in relation to the objectives. In which, some of the stakeholders have emphasised the need to rethink them taking into account aspects such as the market, the varieties of farm types we face and their structures, and therefore the feasibility and profitability of the solutions we present. As for the activities, from the results of the interviews and the workshop, some of them have been.</p> <p>condensed, reducing their number, and specifying more precisely what is to be carried out. The impacts were initially defined in the short and long term, however, after the interviews it was recommended to also make a distinction at the farm and community level, mainly to deal with the different interests that the stakeholders involved may have. Finally, the organisation was very clear, the geographical boundaries, the sector, the technology, were well established from the beginning, so they have not undergone any changes.</p> <p>Problem Definition: Results obtained during the CoP in Wageningen for phase 1 (Recognition) have been refined throughout the stages, adding, and refining the information as well as the stakeholders. For phase 2 (Development), both for the different perspectives and the problem definition itself,</p> <p>validation was requested during the workshop and interviews. For the problem, similar comments to those received for the objectives were recorded (need to broaden and include aspects such as value chain, costs, market, and plausibility of the solutions/problems posed). Finally, phase 3 was directly developed during the workshop, so the results shown in this document are those collected and validated during the session.</p> <p>Resources & Capabilities: The identification of the RCCIs has matured throughout the phases and it has become more and more precise and focused on what we want to do in this LL. Thanks to the interviews and the workshop the lists were successfully completed. The gap analysis has been clarified, at the beginning it was not clear what LL's needs were and therefore what were the requirements that needed to be covered. During the workshop, they were revealed spontaneously and precisely, allowing again to clarify the "hot spots" that need to be addressed</p> <p>Assessment: In general, resources were perceived as less accessible than capabilities when it comes to solving the problem. Financial and organisational resources are the lowest rated. This could be related to the gap found in organisational resources in the previous step. The assessment of technological resources is aligned with the TLR status (3-4) of the facilities.</p>

	<div data-bbox="475 309 1364 817" data-label="Figure"> <table border="1"> <caption>Radar Chart Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Recursos materiales</td> <td>2.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Recursos humanos</td> <td>2.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Recursos financieros</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Recursos tecnológicos</td> <td>3.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Recursos organizativos</td> <td>2.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Capacidades de resolver problemas específico-técnicos</td> <td>3.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Capacidad de innovación</td> <td>4.3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> </div> <p data-bbox="400 864 1444 1070">Human resources are in an intermediate state, since, although we have highly experienced facilitators and coordinators, there is a significant gap in the necessary interdisciplinarity (economists, disseminators, etc.). There is a similar gap in material resources, where tangible technological resources are included. [GAPs found in the previous step]. It is noteworthy that the capability for innovation is the most highly valued, given that we are in the</p> <p data-bbox="400 1099 1444 1305">first steps towards the establishment of an ecosystem for this, the LL. This is accompanied by a high level of technical knowledge for the resolution of specific problems. For the development of the action plan, this evaluation allows us to discern the need to strengthen the actions that involve the use of organisational and human resources and to promote those that depend on our capabilities. As well, to consider activities to access necessary financing.</p> <p data-bbox="400 1335 1444 1440">Changes to Action Plan: The action plan outlined during Wageningen has been substantially modified, evolving into more precise actions aligned with the described needs of the LL (and agreed by its participants).</p>	Category	Score	Recursos materiales	2.8	Recursos humanos	2.8	Recursos financieros	1.8	Recursos tecnológicos	3.3	Recursos organizativos	2.2	Capacidades de resolver problemas específico-técnicos	3.8	Capacidad de innovación	4.3
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<p data-bbox="172 1496 371 1563">UK: Agroforestry in practice</p>	<p data-bbox="400 1496 1444 1601">Definition of Boundaries: At the CoP meeting our views on the delivery of the Living Lab concept began to adapt from a focus on climate factors relating to agroforestry, into the development of a platform for peer-to-peer learning and farmer training.</p> <p data-bbox="400 1630 1444 1803">The initial proposal for the LL was to gather and share information on microclimate impacts of agroforestry and relationship to climate change adaptation/mitigation. Through a series of initial workshops, it became evident that this information was of greater interest to established agroforester and less of a priority for those seeking to establish new agroforestry systems in the UK.</p> <p data-bbox="400 1832 1444 2002">Following the UK workshops and the LL CoP meeting in April 23 we have adapted the UK LL on agroforestry to focus on the development of a platform to facilitate information exchange between farmers & stakeholders across planning, establishment, management market access and links to relevant research etc and to provide a mechanism for peer-to-peer learning and farmer training. This better</p>																

	<p>aligns with the needs of those seeking to adopt agroforestry in the UK, from what is a relatively low baseline agroforestry area.</p> <p>Interviews have consolidated this thinking with knowledge gaps and obstacles to wider adoption of agroforestry as a climate smart practice still evident in farmers minds. Practical elements and direct access to simple economic models are a missing link.</p> <p>Problem definition: <i>Our definition of the problem has changed from one that centred on the Living Lab solutions relating to microclimatic functions of the silvoarable system to a knowledge exchange function around best practice and economics.</i></p> <p>ID and Analysis of Stakeholders: The difference in importance of multi-actor behaviour has been identified and we have reprioritised stakeholders in our communication plans.</p> <p>Resources & Capabilities: [We identified the need for]-the development of a platform to facilitate information exchange between farmers & stakeholders across planning, establishment, management market access and links to relevant research. To provide a mechanism for peer to peer learning and farmer training; -Practical elements and direct access to simple economic models are a missing link.</p> <p>Assessment: <i>The UK living Lab spider web has identified areas which require attention</i>, in broad terms the Living Lab is in a good position in terms of function/facilitation of knowledge exchange around agroforestry as a climate smart farming practice.</p> <div data-bbox="454 1171 1430 1771" style="text-align: center;"> <p>Assessment of the LL conditions (combined)</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Material r.</td><td>5</td></tr> <tr><td>Financial r.</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>Human r.</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>Organisationa l r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Technological r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaboration s r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovations r.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>TM issues</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Attitudes & values</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Absoptive cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Adaptive cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Innovation cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Collaboration cap.</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Cap. To scale</td><td>2</td></tr> </tbody> </table> </div>	Category	Score	Material r.	5	Financial r.	4	Human r.	3	Organisationa l r.	2	Technological r.	2	Collaboration s r.	2	Innovations r.	2	TM issues	2	Attitudes & values	2	Absoptive cap.	2	Adaptive cap.	2	Innovation cap.	2	Collaboration cap.	2	Cap. To scale	2
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<p>SWEDEN: Biogas Västra Skaraborg</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: Through the interviews conducted, we have realised that there are many stakeholders that have an impact, e.g. the Swedish government that decides on state aid for the investment, gas companies that will buy the final product, several authorities involved in environmental permits and other investigations.</p>																														

Problem definition: We thought that one of the problems would be to make it fair for the owners and suppliers of substrates. We thought that the board's knowledge of the technical aspects of building and operating a biogas plant was low. **During the interviews and the workshop, we learned that the knowledge of the board is broad in terms of operation, technical issues, economics, manure and bio-fertilizer management.**

ID and analys of Stakeholders: We started by interviewing the people we had identified as being central to the organisation. **However, we realised that it was important to interview everyone on the board of the limited company, since it was composed of people with different knowledge and backgrounds.** We have also interviewed a couple of major shareholders, to hear their views on the project. To get an overall picture of the challenges, we also conducted an interview with a biogas industry organisation.

Resources & Capabilities: **Within the board and the stakeholder organisation, there is more knowledge about the different parts of the project than we first knew.** This has been a success and has enabled many of the right decisions to be made. It has also turned out that the **municipality and the county administrative board have been very helpful**, which has also helped the project move forward. The **relatively newly appointed CEO** of the company has also played a major role in ensuring that the work has progressed and worked well. This has been emphasised by the authorities in particular.

Assesement: At present, Biogas Västra Skaraborg **has few material resources and still lacks a large part of its capital (both government support and capital from shares). Their capabilities to solve specific technical-management issues to establish LL are currently low because they are on such an early stage in the process and has not yet things like a communication strategy, data management plan etc. However, it has great credibility, a good reputation and a good group of people who have a great commitment to drive the project forward.**

Changes in Action Plan: Since we had our meeting in Wageningen, the Swedish government has presented a budget proposal for more money for "Klimatklivet" (the state support that you can apply for the establishment of biogas). Before, there was a greater uncertainty whether there would be any.

	<p>We have also realised that there is great focus on getting the right type of substrate into the biogas plant. It is also important to choose the right supplier and designer of the plant.</p>
<p>GERMANY: Opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The first idea of the LL was to build on the existing projects and activities based on the Leibniz Innohof (https://leibniz-innohof.de/), keeping the LL “open” to different problems (“use cases”) to be identified case by case with the related stakeholders.</p> <p><i>After the first internal meeting and following the initial feedback from WP4, it was possible to restrict the aim of the LL to topics more closely related to the activities taking place at the InnoHof, with better chances to allow a promising interaction with stakeholders.</i></p> <p><i>The refinement process is still undergoing, but we have identified mainly two sub-topics</i> between the “opportunities to mitigate farm GHG emissions and increase farm resilience”, both dealing with livestock/mixed farming, which is a prominent objective of 1) the InnoHof, 2) local policymakers and 3) the local farming sector. The two sub-topics are, namely, the adaptation/migration at field level (product/process innovation of the cropping systems for livestock production), and the adaptation/mitigation at animal housing level of the livestock systems.</p> <p>Problem Definition: Many practices and potential solutions for mitigation of impacts and adaptation to climate change in livestock systems are available and influenced the initial framing of the aim of the LL. <i>The LL workshop helped to refine the aim of the LL and to narrow the selection of problems to be addressed and solutions to be co-developed.</i> The interests of the stakeholders are still very broad compared with the current capabilities of the LL, but the latter can be developed over time.</p> <p>ID and analysis of Stakeholders: <i>The stakeholder group was (potentially) expanded to WFBB, schools and to a larger group of technology providers and farmers.</i></p> <p>Resources & Capabilities and GAP: <i>We have a better view of the capabilities and resources (e.g., available technological resources and stakeholders). Owing to a better understanding of the aim of the LL, we have also a better understanding of the existing gaps (for instance, human resources). The view on these was very blurred after the first CoP meeting.</i> The need to identify capabilities to be achieved in the future is still persistent.</p> <p>Assessment and Action Plan: Analysing the spider diagram, we can say that the <i>financial and human resources must be improved, with specific emphasis on the latter regard. Collaborations could partially cope with the lack of human resources, but they should also be improved. This partially hampers the capability to cope with technical and management issues and with the capacity to scale up CS solutions.</i> However, the LL in its current status has good innovation potential, good attitudes, adaptive and absorptive capabilities. Material resources should also not be lacking, or at least this is not the most immediate need.</p>

	<p>Changes to Action Plan: <i>The action plan outlined in the first CoP meeting was substantially modified, evolving into more precise actions targeted to clearer aims and to co-develop more concrete CS solutions.</i></p>
<p>FRANCE: Adapting dairy cattle systems to Climate Change, France</p>	<p>Definition of Boundaries: The first idea of the LL was to build on the existing dynamics around both infrastructures that are de AccéLaiR advisory network and the OasYs system experiment running on the long term within the INRAE research station. Events, visits, satellite experimentations are already occurring on these initiatives, but without planned connection and complementarities. After the first meeting and thanks to the inputs of participants, the LL was more envisioned as anchored in these two assets, but enlarged to the possibilities for following up experimental processes led within other facilities, such as the Agricultural High school farm.</p> <p>In Wageningen [CoP], the potential topics to be addressed were both very large and with some specific technical focuses (e.g. the diversification of crops with fodder beetroot). The refinement process is still undergoing, but we have identified more transversal categories of issues that the LL will address: the diversification of fodder sources and trade processes for greater robustness of farming systems regarding feed availability; the value chain lock-ins in terms of specifications required for labels and transformation processes (e.g. quality standards and stability).</p> <p>Problem Definition: Many practices and potential solutions for adapting dairy systems to climate change have been implemented since several years in the OasYs system experiment. The initial problem framing was largely influenced by this context during the Wageningen workshop. Lately, the interviews and the first meeting balanced in a new way the emphasis on the spreading of already experimented practices. Value chain issues, coordination for water management, organisation of experimental processes and knowledge sharing for CC related topics were much more considered in our problem formulation.</p>

	<p>ID and analysis of Stakeholders: The first meeting (June 13, 2023) with identified actors <i>led to considering many other stakeholders than those mentioned on the Wageningen workshop picture. Namely, environmental associations were added to the potential participants, as well as the national institute of origin and quality, the management and accounting offices operating with farmers regarding financial aspects and investment management.</i></p> <p><i>We also reflected on the constant adaptiveness of the consortia: actors may leave or enter the dynamics of the LL, and we need to further anticipate on this and develop processes for active inclusion of new relevant actors</i> (e.g. newsletters are also built in that aim).</p>
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4. Annexes

Annex 1: Link to guidelines

[CFD T4.2 GUIDELINES SET UP A LL.dotm](#)

Annex 2: Link to interview materials

[CFD CoP1 Inspiring Interviews.pdf](#)

[CFD-WP4 Semi structured interview guideline 2023 May 9th.docx](#)

Annex 3: Link to workshop materials

[Set up LLs materials 2023](#)

Annex 4: Link to LLs reports and action plans 2023

[LLs reports & Action plans 2023](#)

Annex 5: Link to LLs progress meeting materials

[Teams sessions Sept 2023](#)

[Teams sessions June 2023](#)

[Teams sessions Oct-Nov 2023](#)

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